

THE USE OF DIDACTIC GAMES AS A SOCIAL PEDAGOGICAL NEED IN MOTHER TONGUE AND READING LITERACY LESSONS OF PRIMARY CLASS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10397132>

Abstract. *This article examines the use of didactic games as a socio-pedagogical necessity in primary school mother tongue and reading literacy classes. It also presents the opinions of world scientists about the importance of didactic games in the teaching process.*

Keywords: *didactic game, elementary school students, elementary education, mother tongue and reading literacy classes.*

Currently, games are widely used not only in preschools, but also in primary and secondary schools. This type of activity is especially important in pedagogy. Unfortunately, students often passively receive new information from teachers. Lessons are short, so students don't have enough time to think about assignments or questions for a long time or to solve problems on their own. Students remember things they observe or experience better than what is told to them. And didactic games used in the lesson can be a way to increase their interest and encourage them to be more active.

Each didactic game has its own educational goals and rules. Didactic games are used not only to make lessons interesting, but also for motivation, explanation, repetition or testing. Prucha defines didactic play as a spontaneous activity of children that achieves certain didactic goals. Didactic games have their own rules, can be held in different places, and also require constant supervision and final evaluation. These are meant to be played not only individually but also in groups. The teacher acts as an organizer and an independent observer at the same time. The author also emphasizes that didactic games cultivate independence, team work, creativity, and also teach students to use previously acquired knowledge and skills.

In primary grades, play is a frequently used teaching method, sometimes more than other methods. For elementary or middle school students, playing games during class may seem boring. However, as mentioned above, we believe that play should be a part of secondary education as it is an activity that accompanies us throughout our lives. Educational games played in the classroom are naturally different from the games children play with their friends at home or in preschool.

Didactic play is an activity that should develop our skills, imagination and creativity. Unlike their own, leisurely games, didactic games are more limited but still fun for kids because they make lessons more interesting and different.

Valishov and Kasikova find that games in general do not have to be productive (motor actions, dice-based games, etc.). According to them, didactic games are more effective on the other hand. They develop our thinking because they are usually based on problematic situations. Like Prucha, Valishova and Kasikova define didactic play as the self-awareness of students guided by certain rules and following educational goals. As mentioned above, students remember things better when they hear, see, smell, or feel them. Students learn a lot of information, vocabulary, or definitions that are not easy to remember. Therefore, it is important to use appropriate techniques

to help students remember it. Games can be aimed at changing a student's attitude towards a particular subject, school subject, school, learning or teacher. Games are useful and fun, they develop students' abilities, skills and fulfill their primary educational goals. Using didactic games in the classroom is useful, but it is important to understand the difference between didactic games and learning. On the other hand, Maniac argues that a didactic game should avoid two extremes. First, the game itself should not exceed the didactic purpose. Second, the goal should not be overemphasized so that the game does not lose its status as a fun activity. Valishova and Kasikova confirm that students always want to win. According to them, didactic games with an element of competition are the most popular among children. These games keep students engaged and encourage them to work together more effectively because they know that working together within a group is the way to success. It depends on the teacher to be able to interest students in interesting, innovative didactic games. These games can serve as a motivating, educational tool to help you achieve your goals.

Teaching children to play has a specific educational purpose. That is the most important importance of the game. The forms and methods of conducting the game differ from other types of education. Didactic game methods are unlimited, it is possible to repeat and change, to add various innovations to it. For example, we repeated 5-7 variations of the game "Silence" with the whole class and with some children more than 10 times, "What has changed?" type game was conducted with 5 different instructional materials. As a result, it is possible to achieve consistent and solid game skills and to be able to listen to and follow each rule of the game.

Didactic games, in terms of their form, are mainly creative games played in kindergarten, which are explained by the teacher by telling a story and as a result of asking students one by one. It is also one-sidedly different from reinforcement games. Didactic games serve the purpose of teaching and are conducted at an interesting, fun, and comprehensible level. Children train with all their heart to win, they get used to completing every given task, as a result, their interest in doing didactic tasks increases. Didactic games help to better understand the purpose of each lesson, the goals and tasks of each exercise. Didactic games include visuality of education, teacher's speech and children's actions, as a result of which unity is born in perception (sight, hearing, skin sensation signs). This encourages children to think about what the teacher said and express what was said, that is, to fulfill the rules of the didactic game themselves. The structure of didactic games in this way makes it possible to analyze the activity of students. That's why all children act with great interest during the game.

There can be no real mental development without play. The game is a spark that arouses enthusiasm and interest in learning in students. The game is a method used by adults - teachers, educators, parents - to form certain qualities in elementary school students. With the help of the game, the learning process of students becomes easier, they learn to deal with various objects, and also the culture of behavior is formed in them. The child's personality is formed by means of the game, in which the mental characteristics related to the organization of educational and work activities and entering into relations with people are formed in the future. Through play, children learn about existence and try to change the world. Thus, the game lays the foundation for the formation of human activity.

In the game, a person shows the ability to reflect existence. The most important importance of the game is that the child's need to influence the world first appears and is formed in it. By school years, game forms develop more widely. The student's game activity is of interest to

scientists of many fields, that is, philosophers, sociologists, biologists, art historians, ethnographers, especially pedagogues and psychologists. In psychology, play is considered to be of crucial importance in the development of the child's psyche. All aspects of a child's personality are formed in unity and interaction only in the game. The game creates an important basis for the transition to a higher stage of development in the child's psyche.

It is the active use of didactic games in the organization of elementary school mother tongue and reading literacy classes that increases students' interest in science. It is the basis for raising questions about the subject or object being studied in science. This indicates that the scope of knowledge of students is expanding. Also, it is recommended that the teacher take into account the situation of the whole class from each didactic game he uses, and also take into account their areas of interest. As a result of this, the effectiveness of the didactic game applied to the teaching process increases even more.

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